

NOISE REDUCTION BY PERFECT ABSORBERS BASED ON ACOUSTIC METAMATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

We have designed a cylindrical perfect absorber based on acoustic metamaterials. The absorber consists of a metamaterial shell that surrounds a center that dissipates the acoustic energy. The metamaterial shell is designed so that perfectly matches the acoustic impedance of the air background and guides the sound to the center. Numerical simulations are reported about the efficiency of the absorber as a function of the absorbing material employed at the center.

Introduction

In the past years, research in metamaterials have attracted great interest in the scientific community. Theoretical and experimental advances have been achieved by scientist in the electromagnetic and acoustic regime. One of the achievements is the theoretical "Black Hole Effect" described by Narimanov [1] and Kildishev [2]. This work has inspired other theoretical articles in electromagnetics [3–5] some of them exploring an impedance matching effect to the Black Hole [6]. Additionally, an experimental demonstration [7] was also reported. In the acoustic realm, composed of ordered arrays of scatterers, known as Sonic Crystals (SC) are used as a class of metamaterial designed to control wave propagation in a medium. In the range of low frequencies (homogenization limit) they behave like homogeneous media whose effective acoustic parameters depend on the lattice filling fraction [8–11]. This homogenization property has been employed to design refractive devices like acoustic lenses [12–14] and gradient index sonic lenses [15–19].

In the present work, we present a perfect acoustic absorber. To ensure an equal performance at any direction, we consider a cylindrical shell around the absorber (core). The shell is not only used to match the impedances of the inner core and the background, but also traps the incoming waves in a Black Hole like falling spiral. The shell is constructed using a SC with a gradient refractive index along the radial component.

This work is divided in three sections. First, the Acoustic Black Hole is described and characterized, then the process to design a structure with this effect will be deeply explained and, finally, the results of the simulation of this black hole structure will be presented.

Acoustic Black Hole

The Acoustic Black Hole is based on a previous proposal [1] done for EM in the microwave regime. Knowing that there is a mapping between the acoustic and the electromagnetic equations [20] it is possible to reproduce this effect with sound propagation. Applying the analogy between them, the solution for designing

the shell to get the Black Hole effect is obtained. Eq. (1) and Eq. (2) are used to get the values of the refractive index, n , as a function of the radial position r :

$$n(r) = \begin{cases} n_b & R_{shell} < r \\ n_b \left(\frac{R_{shell}}{r} \right) & R_{core} < r < R_{shell} \\ n_{core} + i\gamma & r < R_{core} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

$$R_{shell} = R_{core} \frac{n_{core}}{n_b}, \quad (2)$$

where n_b and n_{core} are the refractive index of the fluid background and the core, respectively. R_{core} and R_{shell} are the radius of the core and shell, respectively, and γ is the parameter that gives the absorption property to the core. Finally, i is the imaginary unit. It is also important to note that $R_{core} \geq \lambda/2$ and that the value of R_{shell} is function of n_{core}/n_b . If the difference between the values of the refractive index of the core and the background is small, so is the difference between the radii of the core and the shell, making it difficult to bend the waves.

To test this effect a number of simulations have been made in a commercial finite element simulator (FES). The acoustic properties and size of the structure utilized are listed in Table 1. The structure is embedded in air and the mass density is equal on the three regions. The sound speed of the core is calculated with:

$$c_{core} = \frac{c_b}{n_{core}} - i\eta, \quad (3)$$

where c_b is the background sound speed, n_{core} is the cores refractive index and η is the parameter that gives the absorption property to the core.

Figure 1 shows the black hole "falling" effect. A narrow width Gaussian Beam ($\lambda = 3mm$) impinges the shell at its edge and the wave front starts to bend due the gradient refractive index. The sound travels through the shell and eventually the part of the wave that hits the core is absorbed and the other one either is trapped by the black hole effect or follows a parabolic "escape" trajectory exiting the black hole.

Black Hole Construction

The Black Hole structure design has been divided in two parts: the shell and the core, both embedded in air. Due to the difficulty of fabricating a material with a continuous variation on the refractive index, the shell is constructed from a SC with a hexagonal lattice with lattice parameter $a = 5mm$. On the other

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TABLE 1. GEOMETRIC AND ACOUSTIC PARAMETERS OF THE BACKGROUND AND ACOUSTIC BLACK HOLE USED IN THE FINITE ELEMENT SIMULATOR

Backg.	$\rho_b [\frac{kg}{m^3}]$	n_b	$c_b [\frac{m}{s}]$	
	1.25	347	1	
Core	$R_{core} [mm]$	$\rho_{core} [\frac{kg}{m^3}]$	n_{core}	η
	60	1.25	2.1	2000
Shell	$R_{shell} [mm]$	$\rho_{shell} [\frac{kg}{m^3}]$		
	126	1.25		

$$B_{eff} = \frac{B_b}{1-f}, \quad (4)$$

$$\rho_{eff} = \frac{\Delta(f)+f}{\Delta(f)-f}\rho_b, \quad (5)$$

$$c_{eff} = \sqrt{\frac{B_{eff}}{\rho_{eff}}} = \sqrt{\frac{\Delta(f)-f}{\Delta(f)+f} \frac{c_b}{\sqrt{1-f}}}, \quad (6)$$

$$f_{hex} = \frac{2}{\sqrt{3}}\pi\left(\frac{R_{cyl}}{a}\right)^2, \quad (7)$$

where Δ is a factor that is obtained from [10], where the reader is addressed for further details.

The radius of each cylinder depends on its position. Once the refractive index for certain position is obtained, using Eq.

FIGURE 1. FINITE ELEMENT SIMULATION OF A GAUSSIAN BEAM IMPINGING THE STRUCTURE AND PRODUCING THE BLACK HOLE EFFECT.

hand, the core is a single solid cylinder. Figure 2 shows a scheme of the structure. The black hole consists of the core (red colored circle) and an outer shell formed by 600 cylinders of different radii (green circles).

The shells SC can be considered as a homogenized medium made of subwavelength discrete units. These units are rigid cylinders with different radii. The homogenization method is based on the assumption that, given a finite cluster of rigid cylinders embedded in a fluid or gas background, the scattered field by this cluster in the low frequency limit (approximately $\lambda > 4a$) will be equal to that of a homogeneous compact object with different acoustic properties. The acoustic parameters mainly depend on the fraction of volume occupied by the cylinders in the SC unit cell (filling fraction or f). The next set of equation provide the effective Bulk Modulus (B), mass density (ρ) and sound

(1), then the radius is calculated taking into account the homogenization theory. So, the effective refractive index is obtained from $n(r) = \frac{1}{c_{eff}(f)}$, then using Eq. (7) the radii is calculated. In Figure 2 it is also observed that the radii of the cylinders gets smaller as its position moves away from the core.

The core is designed to be a perfect absorber in the condition that it is perfectly matched to the fluid background surrounding the black hole structure. The absorption of the core is modeled as an factor α added to the wave number as:

$$K_{core} = \frac{2\pi\nu}{c_{core}} + i\alpha, \quad (8)$$

FIGURE 2. SCHEME OF THE STRUCTURE EMPLOYED IN THE MULTIPLE SCATTERING SIMULATION: THE CORE (RED CIRCLE) AND THE SHELL (OUTER 600 GREEN CIRCLES)

speed (c) in function of the filling fraction of a hexagonal cell (f_{hex}).

where v is the linear frequency.

The value of α is obtained with the following steps. It is important to note that the two of the shells main purposes is, one, to match the background acoustic properties with the ones of the core and, two, bend the waves towards the core. First, let us consider a core with the the same acoustic properties as the background ($\rho_{core} = \rho_b$, $c_{core} = c_b$). Then, the wave number is calculated with Eq. (8) stated previously. Finally, the value of α can be obtained using an optimization method that maximizes the absorption in a range of frequencies.

The parameter used to evaluate the absorption of the plane wave is the Intensity Loss (Φ),

$$\Phi = \oint_0^{2\pi} I_r d\theta \quad (9)$$

where I_r is the radial component of the intensity I defined by,

$$I = \frac{1}{2\omega\rho_b} \Re[iP \cdot \nabla P^*] \quad (10)$$

By integrating the intensity flowing through a circle around the structure, we obtain the energy flow in Eq. (9). A value of $\Phi = 0$ is obtained when there is no energy loss, a positive one when energy is created inside the circle and a negative one when there is absorption. So, the more energy is dissipated the more negative its value gets.

Applying the optimization method the value of $\alpha = 26.65$ is obtained. Finally, the real values of velocity and mass density of the core have been taken from the effective parameters of the closest shell cylinder, giving the values of $c_{core} = 240.77m/s$ and $\rho_{core} = 14.599$. Table 2 summarizes the final values of all the acoustic parameters that where obtained during the black hole structure design.

TABLE 2. GEOMETRIC AND ACOUSTIC PARAMETERS OF THE BACKGROUND AND THE STRUCTURE (SHELL + CORE) ACTING AS A PERFECT ABSORBER

	$\rho_b [\frac{kg}{m^3}]$	n_b	$c_b [\frac{m}{s}]$		
Backg.	1.25	1	347		
	$R_{core} [mm]$	$\rho_{core} [\frac{kg}{m^3}]$	n_{core}	$c_{core} [\frac{m}{s}]$	α
Core	60	14.599	1.5	240.77	26.65
	$R_{shell} [mm]$	$\rho_{shell} [\frac{kg}{m^3}]$	$a [mm]$		
Shell	90	1.25	0.5		

$$\Phi = \frac{2}{\omega\rho_b} \sum_q |A_q|^2 [|T_{qq}|^2 + \Re[T_{qq}]] \quad (11)$$

where A_q are the coefficients defining the impinging wave, T_{qq} are the diagonal elements of the t matrix of a cylinder,

For the case of a cluster of cylinders,

$$\Phi = \frac{2}{\omega\rho_b} \sum_q \sum_s \sum_{s'} \Re[A_s A_{s'}^* (\delta_{qs} (T_{eff})_{qs'}^* + (T_{eff})_{qs} (T_{eff})_{qs'}^*)] \quad (12)$$

where \Re is the real part, T_{eff} is the effective t matrix of the cluster and A_s are again the coefficients of the impinging wave.

In brief, a 2D sound wave with a plane wavefront impinges the structure from left to right and a pressure map and the Intensity Loss are calculated. The frequencies analyzed are from 2.5 kHz up to 8.7 kHz in steps of 200 Hz.

Figure 4 shows the results of the Intensity Loss produced by the designed black hole (red curve) and by the solid absorbing cylinder (blue curve). Note that in the range of frequencies [2.7 kHz; 6.6 kHz] the structure is absorbing more energy, having 41% more absorption at a centre frequency of 4.5 kHz.

Figure 5 and Figure 6 show the field pressure map produced by the black hole structure and the solid cylinder respectively at this frequency of 4.5kHz. It is seen that the structure (Figure 5) concentrates the energy in the core due to the black hole effect, and that has less reflectance due the impedance matching,

FIGURE 3. IMPEDANCE (BLUE CURVE) AND REFRACTIVE INDEX (RED CURVE) OF THE CORE AND THE SHELL IN FUNCTION OF THE RADIAL POSITION.

Figure 3 shows the values of the impedance (blue curve) and the refractive index (red curve) of both the core and the shell in function of the radial position r (being the origin of coordinates the center of the core). It can be observed that the impedance and the refractive index are gradually matched with the values of the core.

Numerical Simulations

To demonstrate the Black Hole performance, we have calculated the value of the Intensity Loss described previously. The Intensity Loss of the Black hole is compared with that of a solid cylinder with the same acoustic properties of the core, but having a radius R_{shell} (greater than R_{core}). The numerical simulations are performed using a 2D Multiple Scattering algorithm as described

FIGURE 4. INTENSITY LOSS PRODUCED BY THE PERFECT ABSORBER (RED CURVE) AND THE SOLID CYLINDER WITH R_{shell} (BLUE CURVE)

in [13] and [21].

The expression describing the Intensity Loss Φ in terms of the multiple scattering coefficients is, for a single cylinder:

with the requirements and the effect shown previously with the designed metamaterial cannot be reproduced.

Conclusions

In summary, we have theoretically demonstrated the acoustic black hole effect in the acoustics. Additionally, the shell of the black hole has been proposed by using a 2D GRIN sonic crystal made of rigid cylinders. Numerical simulations prove the efficiency of the proposed structure in a broadband frequency region. It can be concluded that this type of metamaterial shells can be used to improve the absorption performance of some absorbing materials available in nature.

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FIGURE 5. SOUND PLANE WAVE IMPINGING THE SHELL ALONG THE ΓK DIRECTION WITH FREQUENCY $\nu=4.5\text{kHz}$.

FIGURE 6. SOUND PLANE WAVE IMPINGING A CYLINDRICAL SOLID ABSORBER WITH RADIUS EQUAL TO THAT OF THE SHELL SHOWN IN FIGURE 5 WITH FREQUENCY $\nu=4.5\text{kHz}$.

thus achieving more absorption than the solid absorbing cylinder (Figure 6). The physical explanation of the difference of absorption between both configurations is intuitive: More energy is absorbed when more energy enters into the core.

Finally, other numerical simulations have been performed with ordinary materials models like the rubber crum model explained in [22] and the fiber glass model of [23, 24]. These materials have specific acoustic properties that are difficult to match

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